

PRACTICE OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' TECHNICAL SKILLS IN DUTAR PERFORMANCE IN THE FIELD OF MUSIC EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the practical foundations of developing students' performance skills through the dutar, the pedagogical and practical aspects of forming dutar performance techniques, including repertoire selection, the development of proportional movements of the right and left hands, as well as the improvement of simple, reverse, and tremolo strokes techniques. The process of practical lessons, methodological approaches, and effective techniques for developing performance skills are highlighted.*

Keywords: *instrumental performance, dutar, proportionality of right and left hands, performance technique, repertoire selection, tempo, fingering (applicature).*

The formation of performance skills plays a significant role in the professional training of music education students. In particular, for future music teachers, developing performance skills through the dutar not only enhances practical abilities but also strengthens their capability to teach students effectively in pedagogical practice. Therefore, studying the practical foundations of developing students' technical skills in dutar performance is pedagogically relevant.

From a pedagogical perspective, the methodological system of practical lessons is of great importance in teaching dutar performance. During the lessons, repetition, monitoring, individual approaches, and the use of methodological tools increase students' confidence in performance, develop stage culture, and enhance musical thinking. At the same time, relying on national traditions deepens the student's musical taste and enriches performance style, creating the opportunity to teach national instruments to future students.

Repertoire selection is essential in developing technical skills of future music education teachers in dutar performance. The set of pieces performed by a player is called a repertoire. The selected piece should contribute to the student's advancement in performance skills. Successful development of technical skills depends not only on the student's ability but also on appropriate repertoire selection. Gradual increase in

difficulty motivates students and enhances their interest. In other words, the next piece should be more complex than the previous one in terms of performance. It is important that the chosen piece matches the student's abilities to accomplish both artistic and technical tasks. During each stage of learning and teaching dutar performance, the requirements set for the student must be reasonable and appropriate. Excessively difficult pieces can negatively affect learning, while overly simple ones will not promote skill development. A dutar performer, like all instrumentalists, should include pieces from various periods in their repertoire. Applying this principle exposes students to diverse musical materials and broadens their musical horizons [5].

Special attention should be paid to the proportionality of the right and left hands when developing technical skills of future music teachers in dutar performance. Achieving balanced movements of both hands is crucial for quality performance. At the initial stage of learning, it is advisable to study the movements of each hand separately, and later focus on coordinated movement. During performance, both hands must be equally attentive; focusing on only one hand will lead to technical errors. A common problem occurs when the left hand does not reach the correct fret in time, resulting in incomplete or muted sound. Conversely, the right hand may fail to strike in coordination with the left. Practicing scales helps achieve balanced hand coordination.

The tempo also plays an important role in developing dutar performance skills. Tempo determines the speed of musical sounds and is essential in conveying the expressive content of a piece. Correct understanding and control of tempo is a fundamental skill in performance development. In practice, tempos are divided into three main groups: slow, moderate, and fast. During lessons, students learn the characteristics of each tempo and the corresponding techniques. Proper management of tempo helps students form stable performance skills.

Attention must also be given to **applicature** (fingering) in dutar performance. The term "applicature" (from German) means "placing" or "positioning" and refers to the placement and movement of fingers on the strings. Fingering is a key aspect of performance technique development.

Improvement of simple, reverse, and tremolo stroke techniques is essential. While holding the dutar, the lower body rests on the right thigh, and the upper part is held with the right arm near the elbow. The dutar's body should incline slightly upwards, with the end of the neck level with the left shoulder. The handle is positioned between the first finger's proximal and middle joints, with all joints slightly bent over the frets. Left-hand fingers: The fingers pressing the frets are indicated on the musical notes by numbers. The second string is often pressed with the thumb.

In music performance, the method of producing sound is called a stroke. Different strokes give musical pieces their expressive character. Regular practice of various strokes is necessary for mastering dutar technique [1].

In conclusion, the practical foundations of developing dutar performance skills in music education students are an essential part of the educational process. Repertoire selection, hand coordination, and improvement of stroke techniques increase students' performance and pedagogical skills, promote understanding of national musical traditions, and foster stage culture. Therefore, pedagogical approaches and effective methodological systems are key factors in preparing future music teachers.

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